

Young Chemists for Change: Advancing Equity in Chemistry (YCFC-2024)

Report by: Almudena Moreno-Borralló^a, Mary Flood^b, Francesca Adami^b, Wiktorja Brytan^c

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– 31/05/2024

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Science, University
College Dublin

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Organising Committee: Equality, Diversity & Inclusion (EDI) Committee of the Institute of Chemistry of Ireland Young Chemists' Network (ICI-YCN)

Affiliations: ^a Trinity College Dublin; ^b University College Dublin; ^c University of Limerick

Organisation: ICI Young Chemists' Network (ICI-YCN)

Event Sponsors

Royal Society of Chemistry Inclusion & Diversity Fund [Fund 229717881], Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section, Institute of Chemistry of Ireland, UCD School of Chemistry, UCD College of Science, UCD Equality Diversity and Inclusion, ThermoFisher Scientific and Scientific Laboratory Supplies.

Summary

The very first 'Young Chemists for Change (YCFC)' conference was successfully held at University College Dublin on May 30th and 31st of this year, organised by the EDI committee of the ICI-Young Chemists' Network with over 80 attendees and speakers from diverse backgrounds and expertise.

The event hosted a poster session as well as twelve oral presentations, highlighting the opportunity to disseminate research through an EDI-focused lens. Keynote speakers at the event included: Prof. Andrew Nortcliffe (University of Nottingham, UK), who also hosted an interactive workshop with a focus on group discussion and reflection on EDI topics; Dr. Marianne Bore Harr (University College Dublin), and Dr. Niamh O'Mahoney (University College Cork).

Attendees

The event had a total of 85 registered attendees, including postgraduate students, post-doctoral researchers and academic staff. University College Dublin, University of Limerick, Trinity College Dublin, Queen's University Belfast, Maynooth University and Atlantic Technological University, Sligo, were all represented at the event.

Target audience: Postgraduates, Early Career (Academia), Academics.

Programme & Proceedings

The agenda of the event (**Figure 1**) featured a variety of chemistry-related and EDI-focused topics, with keynote speakers from Ireland and the UK, as well as a number of oral presentations from PhD researchers across the country.

Figure 1. Event agenda. Keynote speakers are highlighted in bold. Oral presentations were given by PhD researchers from various institutions across Ireland.

The poster sessions at YCFC (**Figure 2**) allowed attendees to disseminate their research to the wider scientific community, foster valuable knowledge exchange and network with peers, academic staff and industry professionals. This YCFC event also offered the unique opportunity for early career researchers to share their experiences in EDI and its promotion within the chemical sciences.

Figure 2. Poster Session at YCFC.

Alongside these sessions, Professor Andrew Nortcliffe of University of Nottingham provided a highly engaging workshop titled 'Beyond the Mask: Cultivating Authentic Behaviours for an Inclusive Chemical Landscape' (**Figure 3**). The purpose of this workshop was to provide a safe environment for attendees to engage in round-table discussions on a variety of EDI-related topics, such as open communication, active listening, and understanding what it means to be your authentic self. This workshop also provided a shared electronic platform for attendees to submit anonymous opinions in order to gain a deeper understanding and appreciation for diverse perspectives. Additional topics explored included championing of allyship, as well as addressing learned behaviours, micro-aggressions and bias within the chemistry community.

Figure 3. YCFC Workshop provided by Prof. Andrew Nortcliffe (University of Nottingham).

Prizes

Attendees had the opportunity to vote for Best Oral and Poster presentations by scanning a QR code made available throughout the event.

Mark Moloney (ThermoFisher Scientific) presented the 1st Place prize in the Oral Presentations to PhD student Celine Erkey (University College Dublin) for her presentation titled 'Click and Cure: Tailored Building Blocks for Improved Therapeutics'.

Pictured: Mark Moloney (ThermoFisher Scientific) and Celine Erkey (UCD).

Wiktoria Brytan (ICI-YCN) handed the 2nd Place Oral Presentation prize to PhD student Muhammad Zain Bin Amjad (University of Limerick) for his talk entitled 'Synergistic Integration of Silicon-Nanowires on Graphite Substrate for High Performance Lithium-Ion Battery Anodes'.

Pictured: Wiktoria Brytan (ICI-YCN) and Muhammad Zain Bin Amjad (UL).

Almudena Moreno-Borralló (ICI-YCN) handed the Best Poster award to PhD student Christine Coffey (University College Dublin) for her work 'Towards Phosphonium Cations for Catalysis'.

Pictured: Almudena Moreno-Borralló (ICI-YCN) and Christine Coffey (UCD).

Feedback from Attendees at YCFE

"Even at the poster session, I felt like I could ask 'the stupid questions' that I haven't really dared to ask before, and I learnt a lot!"

"I think this workshop allows for all voices to be heard, and for important topics to be discussed."

"I really enjoyed the discussion surrounding how we need to be our authentic selves and find a way to not mask how we are feeling and really be honest with ourselves and others."

"[...] the opportunity to discuss ideas and get others' views in a safe environment."

"I loved the keynote speakers, especially Marianne and Andrew since I found them very relatable and very engaging; I also liked the interactive workshop session."

"[...] the discussions, because I got to learn a lot about other people's experiences and views."

"Talking and discussing together with other people you wouldn't normally chat to on the regular. Broadened my mind more."

"The interactivity and opportunity to talk to others about EDI and be guided by an experienced EDI practitioner"

Pictured: Organising Committee of YCFC with Keynote Speakers (L to R): Prof. Andrew Nortcliffe (UoN), Almudena Moreno-Borrillo (TCD), Wiktoria Brytan (UL), Mary Flood (UCD), Dr. Niamh O'Mahoney (UCC), Dr. Marianne Haarr (UCD), Francesca Adami (UCD).

Acknowledgements

Thanks to the Royal Society of Chemistry Inclusion & Diversity Fund for making this event possible.

Thanks to the Royal Society of Chemistry Ireland Local Section, the Institute of Chemistry of Ireland, the UCD School of Chemistry, the UCD College of Science and UCD Equality Diversity and Inclusion for further funding this event.

Special thanks to ThermoFisher and SLS for sponsoring this event and providing oral presentation and poster prizes.

Thanks to KSG and UCD FoodHall for providing the food and drinks, and to UCD ChemSoc for organising the social event.

Thanks to the ICI-YN, Joseph Byrne, Elaine O'Reilly, James Sullivan and Susan Wilson for their assistance in the organisation of this event.

Research Ethics

Approval for collection of data and comments from attendees was approved as a low risk study by UCD's Human Research Ethics Committee – Sciences, with research ethics reference: LS-C-24-202-Adami-Byrne.